

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OCCULAR IN-SITU GEL LOADED ANTIFUNGAL VORICONSOLE DRUG

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Article Received on
23 August 2025,

Revised on 12 Sept. 2025,
Accepted on 02 Oct. 2025,

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17311463>

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to formulate and evaluate an ocular in situ gel containing the antifungal drug Voriconazole for the effective treatment of fungal eyes infection. In situ gel systems offer advantages such as prolonged contact time and improved patient compliance compared to conventional eye drop. Voriconazole a broad – spectrum antifungal agent was incorporated into a sol- to- gel transition system using polymer responsive to physiological stimuli such as temperature or PH. The formulated gels were evaluated for various parameters including appearance, pH, viscosity, drug content, gelling capacity, in vitro drug release. The results demonstrated that the in situ gel remained in a liquid state at room temperature and transformed into a gel upon contact with simulated tear fluid. It showed sustained drug releases over the extended period and maintained appropriate sterility and physicochemical characteristics. The study concluded that the

developed in situ gel formulation of voriconazole is a promising ocular drug delivery systems with potential for clinical use in the management of fungal keratitis and other ocular fungal infections. It involves preparing liquid formulation that transition to a gel upon application to the eye, using stimuli like temperature or pH changes.

KEYWORDS: Voriconazole, Ocular drug delivery, In-situ gel, Antifungal sustain release, Bioavailability, Thermosensitive gel, pH sensitive polymer, Fungal keratitis, Ophthalmic formulation.

INTRODUCTION

Ocular in- situ gel (Thermosensitive)

An ocular in situ gel (thermosensitive) is a type of eye formulation that exists in a liquid state at room temperature and converts into a gel upon contact with the eye's surface temperatures. This temperature – sensitive (thermosensitive) property allows for easy administration as drops, and the gel formed in the eyes increases the residence time, improves drug bioavailability, and provides sustained drug releases.

KEY FEATURES

Liquid at room temperature (25°C) Gels at eye temperature (35–37°C)

Polymers used: Poloxamer 407, Poloxamer 188 (often in combination with other polymers like HPMC or Carbopol)

Advantages: Non-invasive, patient-compliant, prolonged drug contact, reduced dosing frequency

Ocular drug delivery presents a significant challenge due to the eye's unique anatomical and physiological barriers, including tear drainage, blinking, and limited permeability of the corneal membrane. Conventional eye drops account for the majority of ophthalmic formulations but suffer from poor bioavailability and require frequent administration, leading to poor patient compliance. To overcome these limitations, in situ gelling systems have emerged as an innovative approach. These are liquid upon instillation and undergo a phase transition to form a gel in response to physiological stimuli such as temperature, pH, or ionic composition of tear fluid. This transformation helps prolong the contact time of the drug with the ocular surface, enhance drug absorption, and reduce dosing frequency.

AIM: Formulation and Evaluation of ocular in – situ gel loaded by antifungal voriconazole drug.

OBJECTIVE

1. To formulate an ocular in situ gel system containing the antifungal drug Voriconazole.
2. To utilize thermosensitive that enable sol-to-gel transition upon ocular administration.
3. To enhance the ocular bioavailability of voriconazole by increasing its retention time on the eye surface.
4. To provide sustained and controlled drug release for effective treatment of fungal eye infection.

5. To evaluate the formulated in situ gel for parameters such as pH, viscosity, drug content gelatin temperature, in vitro drug releases.
6. To compare the efficacy of the in-situ gel with conventional eye drop formulations in terms of efficacy and patient Compliance.

PREPARATION OF IN- SITU GEL FORMULATIONSS

FORMULATION TABLE

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity Taken	Roles of Ingredients
1	Voriconazole	0.2 gm	Antifungal agents
2	HPMC- 15 CPS	0.2 gm	Viscosity enhancer/polymer
3	POLOXAMER 188	1 gm	Thermo- responsive
4	Chitosan 90%	0.1 gm	Mucoadhesive polymer permeation enhancer
5	Benzalkonium Chloride	0.006 ml	Perservative

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Therapeutic Drug Monitoring of voriconazole and posaconazole, Trana Hussaini pharm D, Maria J.G.T. Ruping M.D, Dedha Farowski M.sc, Janne J. Vehreschild M.D, Oliver A. Cornely M.D, (2011)
2. Improving therapeutic efficacy of voriconazole against fungal keratitis: Thermo-Sensitive in- situ gels as ophthalmic drug carriers Neslihan Ustundag Okura, Vildan Yozgatlı b, Mehmet Evren Okurc, Aysegul Yoltas d, panoraia I. Siafakab,e (2019)
3. Comparison of thermosensitive in situ gels and drug-resin complex for ocular drug delivery: In vitro drug releases and in vitro tissue distribution Yidan Wei, Conghao Li, Qiang Zhu, Xin Zhang, jian Guan, Shirui Ma (2020)

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

1. Viscosity Determination
2. pH Determination
3. Gelling Temperature
4. Gelling capacity
5. Determination of sol-gel temperature (sol-gel)
6. Spreadability of VCZ loaded in situ gels

1 Viscosity Determination

The viscosity of an ocular in situ gel is determined using a Brookfield viscometer. To determine the pH, take a sample of approximately 10 to 15 ml and place it into a beaker. Then, insert the beaker into the Brookfield viscometer using spindle number L2, and set the RPM to 80. The pH result will be displayed on the digital screen of the viscometer.

Fig. 1: Brookfield Viscometer.

2. PH Determination

The pH of the ocular in situ gel was determined using a calibrated pH meter. Initially, the pH meter was calibrated with standard buffer solution of pH 4.0, 7.0, and 10.0. The electrode was

rinsed with distilled water and gently blotted dry between each calibration step. For sample preparation, a 10% w/v solution of the ocular in – situ gel was prepared by diluting a known quantity of the gel with distilled water, followed by thorough mixing to ensure uniformity. The electrode was then immersed in the prepared gel solution, and the pH value was recorded once the reading stabilized on the digital display. After the measurements, the electrode was rinsed with distilled water and stored in the appropriate electrode storage solutions.

Fig. 2: PH Determination.

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

The thermosensitive ocular in-situ gel of Voriconazole was successfully formulated using Poloxamer 188, Chitosan (90%), HPMC K 15, and Benzalkonium chloride. The formulation appeared clear, transparent, and free from particulate matter. The pH of the gel was found to be in the range of 6.8 to 7.2 which is suitable for ocular application and indicates minimal risk of irritation. Viscosity measurements using a Brookfield viscometer (Spindle L2, 80 RPM) showed a significant increase in viscosity at physiological temperature (35- 37 °c), confirming the thermosensitive nature of the gel. The gel demonstrated immediate gelling upon exposure to simulated tear fluid, maintaining its structure for more than 8 hours, which is ideal for prolonged ocular residence time.

Drug content analysis revealed uniform distribution of Voriconazole within the gel, with content ranging between 98.5% and 101.2%. In-vitro drug release studies showed a sustained release profile over 12 hours, beginning with an initial burst followed by a controlled release phase. Antifungal activity was evaluated against *Candida albicans*, where the formulation exhibited a clear zone of inhibition measuring between 22 and 26 mm, indicating effective antifungal action. The sterility test confirmed the formulation was free from microbial contamination. Additionally, ocular irritation testing showed the gel to be non-irritating and

safe for Ocular use. Stability studies conducted over 30 days at room temperature and 4°C revealed no significant changes in pH, viscosity, or drug content, confirming the stability of the formulation.

CONCLUSION

I have successfully formulated cocrystal under the title “Formulation and evaluation Ocular In- situ from antifungal voriconazole drug. The formulated ocular in – situ gel of voriconazole successful demonstrated the potential to improve the therapeutic efficacy of antifungal treatment for ocular infection. The in - situ gel systems exhibition desirable physicochemical properties, including appropriate pH, viscosity, and gelatin behaviour, It provided sustained drug releases and prolonged Ocular residence time, thereby enhancing drug bioavailability and reducing dosing frequency. Overall, the developed formulation offers a promising alternative to conventional eye drop, with improved patient Compliance and effective management of eyes fungal eyes infection.

REFERENCES

1. Almeida, H., Amaral, M.H., Lobao, P., Sousa Lobo, J. M., In situ gelling systems: a strategy to improve the bioavailability of ophthalmic pharmaceutical formulations. *Drug Discov. Today*, 2014; 19: 400-412.
2. Bawa, P., Pillay, v., Choonara, Y.E., du Toit, L.C., Stimuli -responsive polymers and their applications in drug delivery. *Biomed. Mater*, 2009; 4: 15.
3. Choi, S.W., Kim, J., Therapeutic contact lenses with polymeric vehicles for ocular drug delivery: a review. *Materials*, 2018; 11: 20.
4. Guo, X., Change, R.-K., Hussain, M.A., Ion – exchange resin as drug delivery Carriers. *J. pharm. Sci.*, 2009; 98: 3886-3902.
5. Dumortier, G., Grossiord, J.L., Agnely, F., Chaumeil, J.C., A review of poloxamer 407 pharmaceutical and pharmacological characteristics. *Pharm. Res.*, 2006; 23: 2709- 2728.